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Validation of non-formal and informal learning: The hero with a thousand faces?

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Abstract

Validation of non-formal and informal learning has been gaining political momentum in Europe within the implementation of lifelong learning policies since the early 2000s. Policy documents claim a variety of education, socio-political and economic benefits from the implementation of validation, making validation a *hero* for lifelong learning. This article discusses the concept of validation of non-formal and informal learning and provides an overview of the different *faces* and interpretations of validation. Starting with the terminology, the article discusses related terms such as recognition, prior learning, assessment, accreditation or certification and their different connotations. Principles and aspects that characterise the current use of validation as a policy priority in Europe are presented. The article highlights the major themes on validation and their implications for policy and research.

KEYWORDS: Validation of non-formal and informal learning, recognition of prior learning, accreditation, certification, review, Europe

¹ The views expressed in this article are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect those of Cedefop.

1 INTRODUCTION

Validation of non-formal and informal learning has been gaining political momentum in Europe within the implementation of lifelong learning policies since the year 2000, and especially after the 2012 Council Recommendation on validation (Villalba-García & Bjørnåvold, 2017). In the impetus for the development and implementation of lifelong learning policies at the beginning of the century, there has been an increasing emphasis on the importance of creating educational systems that allow for diverse pathways with no dead-end. The constant need for learning implies also that learning is not only confined to formal educational institutions, but it occurs at any moment, and all learning is valuable. In this context, validation of non-formal and informal learning is a fundamental element of the realisation of lifelong learning.

The validation of non-formal and informal learning is usually connected to different educational, socio-political and economic benefits (Baigorri-López, Martínez-Cía & Monterrubio-Ariznabarreta, 2006; ICF & 3s Unternehmensberatung GmbH, 2020; Svetlik, 2009). Policy documents usually argue that validation can contribute to the development of more flexible and adaptable education and training systems (Leitner, Pausits, Giesecke, Schartinger, Kalcik & Keser Aschenberger, 2000). Validation has been a key instrument, along with the development of credit systems and modularisation, for increasing the flexibility and permeability of formal education (Colardyn & Bjørnåvold, 2004; Prawelska-Skrzypek, Jalocho, Shapira, Brogan, Lafont, Pariat, Marinic & Ivosevic, 2013). Individuals that do not fulfil formal requirements to access a certain level of education, for example people lacking a school leaving certificate to access tertiary education, can have access through validation to university or other formal programmes. By certifying knowledge and skills that have been acquired outside formal education institutions, less traditional learners from low socio-economic backgrounds, or elderly people, can access higher levels of education using the learning acquired through life outside the classroom settings. Similarly, the youth sector has paid increasing attention to validation. Through validation, young people that might lack qualifications and work experience to access certain jobs, can boost their employability by certifying knowledge and skills acquired through voluntary work or during leisure activities (Council of the European Union, 2011; Schild & von Hebel, 2006).

This capacity of granting access and new opportunities for early leavers from education and training and other non-traditional groups, has connected validation to issues of social inclusion and equity. The claim is that validation will help vulnerable groups and those unemployed or at risk of unemployment to re-enter the labour market, gain employment or re-engage in education and training, creating new opportunities for them (Council of the European Union, 2012; Leita, 2020; Leushuis & Van den Brande, 2020; Wagner, Childs & Constable, 2003). The financial crisis in 2008 and the crisis brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic have also contributed to an increase in unemployment, and especially youth unemployment, as well as a renewed interest in up-skilling and re-skilling workers (European Commission, 2020b; Klein-Collins, 2020). Validation can contribute to help in redirecting people's careers by providing access to new qualifications while reducing the time spent for obtaining a qualification as the individual might be granted certain credits or exemptions based on their work or life experience. In addition, through a validation process, an individual's knowledge and skills are made *official*, signalling that the holder possesses a certain level of competences, contributing to their employability (Seidel, Bretschneider, Kimmig, Neß & Noeres, 2008).

Further, the increasing level of globalisation and competition in the “war for talent” (Michaels, Handfield-Jones & Axelrod, 2001) has also given impetus to validation. Validation is associated with a better match between the demand and supply of skills in society as a whole (Pouliakas, 2012). Employers can understand, through validation—at least theoretically—the full spectrum of the existing skills supply of the population, not restricted to the limitations of formal education curricula. In this sense, validation can contribute to finding a more diversified skills supply, better tailored to employer’s specific needs and requirements. Through validation employers can better match their skill demand, as validation provides proof that the individual has certain skills (Cedefop, 2014). This played an important part in the importance given to validation during the 2015 migration crisis, making validation a tool for integration and social inclusion (European Commission, EACEA & Eurydice, 2019; Hopkins, 2013, p. 92). Through validation, migrants can certify and make visible their skills, providing thus a skill supply to the labour market. Validation, thus, permits better allocation of resources in the labour market and facilitates integration (OECD, 2017).

Finally, there is also an increasing interest in individualising learning paths and careers for which validation can be also a relevant tool (Andersson, Halttunen & Nistrup, 2020; Ralphs, 2011). Validation allows to better tailor training to meet the needs of individuals. By determining what the person knows before the beginning of a programme, it is possible to grant specific parts of the programme and for the individual to learn only those modules or parts that they do not know, not only shortening their training time, but also making it more tailored to their specific needs.

This versatility of validation to be used for different purposes and within different policy domains has given it a relevant stand in the development of lifelong learning policies in Europe and elsewhere. However, this has also become one of its main weaknesses as the different traditions and objectives of validation result in limited conceptual clarity. The multiplicity and diverse range of objectives and connections to different policy domains has resulted also in a rather fragmented landscape of validation practices across Europe that have been developed in parallel, sometimes with no relationship between them. There are differences across countries but also within countries and sectors, in the way validation is defined and approached (Cedefop, European Commission & ICF, 2019). The lack of a common definition of validation might also be a factor contributing to the lack of appropriate monitoring mechanisms at the national or regional level (Cedefop, European Commission & ICF, 2016). This might also have implications for funding frameworks (Cedefop et al., 2016). Without a clear understanding of what validation is, and what it involves, this may affect the extent to which (sufficient) funding is provided for implementation. In addition, the lack of a common definition makes it difficult to carry out cost and benefit analyses. Also for research, Wihak (2012) argues that the difference in terminology and conceptualisation causes problems when searching academic databases.

This article presents a critical analysis of validation and its conceptualisation over the last two decades and implications for policy and research mainly in the European context. An objective of the article is to discuss and clarify the terminology around the concept of validation and similar concepts such as prior learning assessment or accreditation of prior learning and the relationship between validation and skills identification, assessment and certification.

2 VALIDATION: A THOUSAND FACES

Part of the problem in establishing validation as a field of enquiry is the large variety of terms used to refer to it (Judy & Wihak, 2017), sometimes used interchangeably without a clear delimitation of how the terms differ. Aggarwal (2015) highlights that there is no standard terminology to refer to validation of non-formal and informal learning and lists several acronyms that are used across the globe. The expressions used include: Assessment of prior experiential learning (APEL); accreditation of prior experiential learning; assessment of prior learning (APL); Prior learning assessment (PLA); Prior learning assessment and recognition (PLAR); Recognition of acquired competences (RAC); Recognition of acquired skills (RAS); Recognition of current competences (RCC); Recognition of non-formal and informal learning (RNFIL); Recognition of prior learning (RPL); Recognition, validation and certification of competences (RVCC); Validation of non-formal and informal learning (VNFIL); Validation of prior learning (VPL); Recognition of professional qualifications; Recognition, validation and accreditation (RVA), etc. In addition, concepts such as skills audits, skills or competence assessment and skills identification are also used interlinked with validation. All terms encompass related notions of similar processes, related to making visible and providing value to the knowledge and skills that individuals have. The terms and expressions used have two main parts underlying the construct. One part focuses on the action being carried out: accreditation, assessment, recognition or validation. The other part refers to what is being validated: prior learning, non-formal and informal learning, experiential learning, and so on.

Starting from the latter, some terms refer to learning, while others refer to the outcomes of learning: acquired competences, prior skills or current competences. There are also different terms that modify learning. *Experiential* emphasises that the validated learning has been acquired through experience, contrasting it to learning that has been taught or transferred. *Prior* focuses on when learning occurred, referring to learning before the validation (accreditation or recognition) process. *Non-formal* and *informal learning* emphasise the context in which learning takes place, excluding learning in formal institutions. Prior learning can be considered broader than the others, as it can include all forms of learning in all different contexts; something well suited for the philosophy of lifelong learning underpinning the theme. On the other hand, processes for the validation (accreditation or recognition) of learning might differ considerably depending on how the learning was acquired. Murphy and Dewosky (2018) warned about the use of non-formal learning together with informal learning, as the nature of these forms of learning are very different. Nevertheless, all expressions underline the importance of having a life-wide perspective on learning, in which learning is valuable independent of where and when it has been acquired.

The other part of the expression referring to what is being carried out uses terms interchangeably. Accreditation is normally connected to the awarding of academic credits to individuals with the aim of shortening an educational program—in most cases, in the context of higher education degrees. It is thus a term normally associated with access and exemptions through the awarding of credits. However, accreditation is also associated with the process by which an institution is evaluated and certified to be able to deliver educational programs. Also, it is through accreditation that an educational institution obtains a quality standard (Glidden, 1996). Recognition is normally broader than accreditation. It is more often connected to vocational and professional training institutions in addition to university approaches. Recognition is often used as a process by which an education institution (often higher

education institutions, sometimes other institutions) or a governmental body determines if a foreign-acquired qualification corresponds to qualifications in a specific country (Hawthorne, 2013). Similarly, recognition is sometimes connected to processes of licensing or access to professions. In this meaning, recognition refers to a process in which a sectoral institution determines if an individual is qualified to exercise a profession. Recognition is, thus, usually associated with a broader process, more connected to formal qualifications and regulated professions. The term validation comes from the Latin *to make valid*. It was adopted and promoted mainly within the European context, probably as a direct translation of the French system of *Validation des Acquis de l'Experience* (VAE). Annen and Bretschneider (2014) indicated that validation is used both as an overarching term or only as one part of the whole process. As one part of the process, *validation* is used interchangeably with *assessment*, referring to the moment in which the individual is evaluated against specific standards.

The combination of these different terms and expressions results in a large variety of possible expressions. Each one works in its own context and for its own purpose and to a large extent is understood by the different stakeholders that use it and implement it. This makes an overview of validation across countries and contexts difficult. Underlying them all, nevertheless, there are two fundamental principles: All learning, irrespectively of how and when it has been acquired is valuable and the value of learning can be somehow certified in order to provide it with utility. The next section presents a brief overview of the historical developments in the field to provide some more clarity on different uses of validation terminology and its nuances. While the focus of the analysis presented is on European development, references to other regions support a wider understanding.

3 THE ROAD TO A COMMON UNDERSTANDING OF VALIDATION?

Murphy and Dębowski (2018) argue that the genesis of policies for valuing learning outside formal education is frequently attributed to Faure (1972) and Delors (1998); a development associated to lifelong learning policies (Duvekot, Schuur & Pulusse, 2005). Michelson (1999) argues that RPL has its roots in American pragmatism, based on the learning philosophy of Dewey for whom “[instruction starts] with the experience learners already have [...] this experience and the capacities that have been developed during this course proved the starting point for all further learning” (Dewey, 1938, p. 74; Harris, 2018). Thakrar (2006) places the origin in the Co-operative Assessment of Experiential Learning (CAEL) study that investigated how experiential learning could be given academic credit or recognition (Willingham, 1976). Rooted in Dewey’s philosophy of education, in this first phase, the most commonly used expression was *accreditation of prior experiential learning* (APEL) (Colley, Hodkinson & Malcom, 2003). These developments were encouraged by the expansion of higher education in the 1980s and 1990s mainly driven by UK and US universities. By awarding credits, it was possible to attract more students, from a broader background, while shortening study time. This resulted in the development of methodologies for APEL and different ways of seeing experiential learning (Colley et al., 2003; Fenwick, 2001).

Already in its origin, two distinct objectives for validation can be found. Trowler (1996) talks about the contrasting approaches to credit exchange and the developmental models in the accreditation of experiential learning. This distinction is still a source of discussion and an on-going debate in the area of validation. In the first case, the process refers to credit exchange

or summative approaches, where the aim of the process is to certify a certain level of skills, knowledge or competences an individual has. In the second case, the formative or developmental approaches focus on increasing the understanding of the individual of their own skills and knowledge.

In 1997, in Europe, the Lisbon Recognition Convention (Council of Europe, 1997) developed by the Council of Europe and UNESCO, put forward an agreement to ease the mobility of higher education students. With the Convention, unless substantial difference can be shown, diplomas obtained in one country should be accepted in another country and countries commit to recognise reciprocally the *general requirements for access to higher education* (Council of Europe, 1997). While the recognition convention and its further elaboration in the Bologna process (European Commission, 2020a) refers to formal qualifications, in some of the signing countries the existing access requirements included prior learning assessment. Thus, in some instances, the recognition of formal diplomas was connected to accreditation of experiential learning or any other learning outside formal institutions. Thus, recognition of prior learning tends to be more associated with learning in formal contexts and access to higher education, and with the summative approaches to validation.

Around the end of the 1990s, South Africa established a system for recognition of prior learning (RPL) in connection with the development of the National Qualification Framework. The system was created to compensate for the existing inequalities in educational achievement due to apartheid (Allais, 2009; Osman, 2003). Similarly, developments in validation in Australia and New Zealand can be associated with efforts to include aboriginal and other traditionally excluded students into higher levels of education (Strathdee, 2009; Wagner et al., 2003; Wheelahan, 2009). Young (2010) has referred to RPL as the tool to make certain learning that has been traditionally excluded is accepted, emphasising the power dynamics associated with validation and its role in contributing to social justice. Singh (2015, p. 22) argues that validation can contribute to equalising different “cultures of knowledge”. For her, each sector of education will normally be driven by different legal frameworks, rules and practices and validation serves to create bridges between different forms of learning (Cooper, Ralphs, & Harris, 2017).

Two years before the Lisbon Convention, the European Commission White Paper on Teaching and Learning (European Commission, 1995) emphasised the importance of recognising competences acquired outside formal education. The 2001 Communication from the Commission for making the European area of lifelong learning a reality (European Commission, 2001) emphasised the life-wide perspective of learning already addressed in the European Commission white paper on Teaching and Learning (European Commission, 1995). This gave important impetus to valuing learning that occurs outside formal educational settings (Rubenson, 2001). During the next decade, validating learning acquired outside a formal education institution would become a central element in EU projects studying different ways of implementing and organisation systems for validation as well as transferability of learning outcomes from context to context; for example, based on credit transfer systems and mobility measures. This was connected to the development of first Cedefop’s validation inventories (Bjørnåvold & Colardyn, 2005) aiming at providing an overview of validation practices in Europe for countries to learn from each other. These different initiatives provided ground for experimentation and exploration of the concept as well as the bases for its expansion in the following years.

The Copenhagen Declaration of 29–30 November 2002 launched the European strategy for enhanced cooperation in Vocational Education and Training (VET), commonly referred to as the *Copenhagen process*. It also established the need for “developing a set of common principles regarding validation of non-formal and informal learning with the aim of ensuring greater compatibility between approaches in different countries” (European Ministers of Vocational Education and Training, and the European Commission, 2002, p. 2). In 2004, the Council presented the conclusion on common European principles for the validation of non-formal and informal learning (Council of the European Union, 2004), which established the basic common denominator for how to carry out validation in Europe. Also in 2004, the Council Decision on a single Community Framework for the transparency of qualifications and competences in Europe, *Europass*, published a series of European level templates that could be used for the documentation of learning outcomes in different contexts, including those acquired through non-formal and informal learning (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2004). In 2006, the Youthpass introduced a similar idea to Europass, providing a common template for the documentation of voluntary work (SALTO, 2020). This constituted a first articulation for documenting learning outcomes in the context of youth policy. Civil society organisations and youth organisations increasingly engaged in discussions about validation of non-formal and informal learning. In 2008, the Council Recommendation on the establishment of the European Qualification Framework for Lifelong Learning asked Member States to use the European Qualification Framework (EQF) as a reference tool to compare the qualification levels of different qualification systems (Council of the European Union, 2008). The Recommendation establishes that the EQF should facilitate the process and the development of validation arrangements. These developments, connected with an increasing definition of qualifications in terms of learning outcomes made validation a much more feasible possibility in Europe and established a foundation for a more common approach. Several countries developed validation arrangements in connection to their development of NQFs and its referencing process to EQF.

The main concern, especially in the first half of the 2000s was transferability of learning from context to context (including mobility actions) and developing flexible and *permeable* education systems. Around the end of the first decade of 2000, a perspective in which validation was seen as a tool for increasing employment and social justice perspectives became more prominent, partly influenced by the financial crisis. The 2008 financial crisis saw an increase on unemployment, especially youth unemployment, and added pressure on labour markets to function better and more transparently. This made validation more prominent in labour market policy discussions. In 2010, the European Trade Union confederation, for example, commissioned a study on validation with the aim of putting validation of non-formal and informal learning “at the core of trade union strategies for education and training in Europe” (Visentini, 2014, p. 9). Youth policies also increasingly underscored the role of validation for providing easier access to employment based on validated experience (European Youth Forum, 2008).

4 THE 2012 EUROPEAN COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION ON VALIDATION

The Recommendation of December 2012 can be regarded as the beginning of a new stage for validation in Europe (Villalba-Garcia, Souto-Otero & Murphy, 2014; Villalba-García & Bjørnåvold, 2017). The Recommendation calls all EU member states to establish by 2018 arrangements for validation of non-formal and informal learning that enables individuals to:

“(a) have knowledge, skills and competences which have been acquired through non-formal and informal learning validated [...]; (b) obtain a full qualification, or, where applicable, part of a qualification, on the basis of validated non-formal and informal learning experiences” (Council of the European Union, 2012, p. 3). These two main objectives mirrored the basic distinction between summative and formative approaches to validation, putting more emphasis on the summative approach, especially in option b. The recommendation provides also a definition for validation that to a large extent allows for a more stable development of policies in the area. It defines validation as “a process of confirmation by an authorised body that an individual has acquired learning outcomes measured against a relevant standard and consists of the following four distinct phases: Identification [...], documentation[...], assessment[...] and certification[...]” (Council of the European Union, 2012, p. 5).

The recommendation signals a political commitment to validation policies (Villalba-García & Bjørnåvold, 2017) and illustrates an agreement on certain basic principles of validation (Villalba-García, 2016). These can be seen as a minimum common denominator for validation practices across Europe. The principles of the recommendation were further expanded in the European Guidelines for Validation (Cedefop, 2015). The guidelines point to the main themes to take into consideration when designing, developing and implementing validation systems in Europe. The following section discusses briefly the main aspects of these principles while addressing main policy and research implications.

4.1 The individual at the centre

The European guidelines clearly emphasise the need to put the individual at the centre of validation (Cedefop, 2015). The validation process needs to be designed to meet individual needs. Through validation it is possible for the individual to have a better understanding of what their skills and competences and deficits are in relation to specific standards. Following the APEL tradition rooted in Dewey’s educational philosophy, any learning starts in what the individual has learned previously. Validation, thus, becomes a pedagogical tool (Andersson, 2017; Duvekot, 1997; Rickabaugh, 1997). In this sense, validation is a necessary condition to individualise the learning pathway. Through a process of validation, it is possible to tailor the training offer to the specific needs of the individual. This is increasingly emphasised in policy documents and there is a tendency in education and training policies to create conditions for tailoring education and training provision. Rubenson (2003) has argued that the emphasis on lifelong learning implies the notion of the individual as the *enterprise of one-self*. Any experience can become a learning opportunity and the lines between what constitute learning, training and simply working or carrying out an activity are getting blurred. In this sense, through validation the individual reflects upon previous experiences and realises what learning has occurred and how this learning might be formalised or connected to existing standards. Validation becomes, in this way, a tool for self-development and empowerment. Individuals with a low level of qualifications realise that they have certain valuable skills and competences that can help them in advancing their careers or accessing a qualification. Several studies have shown that an outcome of validation is an increase in the level of self-confidence and confidence in skills (Miguel, Ornelas & Maroco, 2016; Peters, 2000; Whittaker, 2011). However, the evidence draws mostly on small scale studies; there is a lack of large scale research. More research is needed as there is little information on what factors might better facilitate this type of empowerment of individuals.

The emphasis on the individual requires necessarily adequate systems of support to translate experiences into documentation of learning outcomes that can be assessed and certified. Guidance before, during and after the validation process is important to reap all validation benefits (Cedefop, 2015). Further understanding that how Career guidance and validation are interlinked and in what they interact with other support measures, including financial resources are gaining political interest. The current discussion on Individual Learning Accounts in the context of the European skills agenda is an example of this (European Commission, 2020b).

4.2 The authorised body

In addition of being a tool for individualisation and tailoring educational provision to specific individual needs, individuals become part of a specific community through validation. Validation enables individuals to obtain access to a certain level of education or to obtain a qualification or certificate that grants access to a profession. In this way, the *authorised body* that delivers validation becomes the gatekeeper of the profession. It is this institution that decides what constitutes *acceptable knowledge* and validation can thus be a tool both for inclusion and exclusion. Studies on the recognition of foreign qualifications and access of migrants into formal education has shown certain difficulties of some groups to access and succeed in validation processes. Differences between *cultures of knowledge* might mean that certain knowledge and skills are not considered acceptable.

It is also the authorised body providing the certification that determines the value of the certificate obtained. The value and trust in the certificate depends necessarily on who awards it. If the institution awarding the certification is perceived as trustworthy and of high quality, the associated certificate is usually regarded as valid and reliable. Qualifications awarded on behalf of national authorities are usually trusted and are backed-up by quality assurance mechanisms. In several countries, the quality assurance of the validation process is embedded in the quality assurance and controls of the education institutions that provide them. However, there seems to be a certain tendency to create specific quality assurance frameworks for validation (Cedefop et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the ultimate goal of validation is that the individual can utilise the skills and knowledge validated.

Even if a person has certified skills, these must ultimately be recognized by those who can use them, value them and are willing to pay for them—the employers. The real recognition of skills takes place on the labour market. It is their practical value that makes the difference—in hiring, career and skills development pathways, promotion and remuneration. (Braňka, 2016, p. 27)

How certifications provided outside formal institutions can be quality assured and their value determined remains a question. With the increasing variety of learning providers and types of certifications (micro-credentials, badges, etc.) these will become even more important in the coming years. The Recommendation of the Council of the European Union (2012) asks different stakeholders to get involved in the development and implementation of validation. It is through this involvement that the different stakeholders can understand and value the outcomes of the validation process. However, these types of *real recognition* of skills might have other than only labour market related objectives.

4.3 A variety of objectives

The 2012 Recommendation defines validation as a process and divides it into four stages that address different objectives of validation. The phases allow for the articulation of the concept of validation across Europe and its adaptation to different national contexts. Depending on what is the main objective of a validation process, emphasis will be placed in a specific phase. The identification and documentation phases are more related to formative approaches, while assessment and certification are more connected to summative approaches.

Pokorny and Whittaker (2014) add to summative and formative, predictive and transformative objectives of validation. Predictive objective refers to validation in recruitment processes, where making skills and competences visible aims at determining if the person will succeed in their job position. The transformative objective implies the transformation of the individual going through the process of validation. Duvekot et al. (2005, p. 3), within the formative and summative approaches differentiate between six functions of validation: (1) the development, realisation and self-respect of the individual; (2) the (re)-entry into the labour market and improving the flexibility of the labour market; (3) company-specific objectives in which validation is used for internal training, job evaluation; (4) planning training and further learning; (5) enrichment of the company/society and (6) reduction of unemployment and skills mismatch.

In practice, these different objectives might occur concurrently. Validation practices carried out in the third sector tend to have a formative character and emphasise the first two stages, while in the vocational training sector, validation arrangements tend to award a full or parts of a qualification, so the emphasis is on the last phase. However, validation in the third sector can be connected to a summative approach if the learning outcomes that are identified and documented can be assessed against some formal education standards and certified. What is maybe more important for validation to fulfil its full potential is that the four phases remain coherent in terms of the learning outcomes and standards they address.

4.4 Learning outcomes, standards and qualification frameworks

In Europe, in a majority of the countries, the capacity to validate non-formal and informal learning is given to education institutions (Cedefop et al., 2019). They are made the sole guard of what constitutes *acceptable* knowledge and skills. In this way, knowledge and skills acquired outside formal education institutions is in a sense *brought back* and made formal, comparing it to formal education standards. The European guidelines highlight the importance of making sure that standards used in validation are similar and equivalent to those used in formal education. Otherwise there is a risk of creating qualifications that are of different value (Cedefop, 2015). This is the way of bridging the different *Cultures of knowledge*.

However, learning acquired in non-formal and informal settings might, in many instances not have a clear equivalent in formal educational programmes (Cedefop et al., 2019). In countries in which educational programmes change very slowly and the feedback between education provision and labour market needs is slow, a lot of the learning occurring outside formal

institutions might be very relevant for the labour market, but not be properly reflected in formal education curricula (Cedefop, 2013). This translates into a parallel system of certifications and credentials that industry might use and that are not clearly connected to formal education outcomes.

With the diversification of training providers, more and more credentials are appearing, with diverse and sometimes unclear value. The development and implementation of national qualification frameworks has aimed at increasing the transparency of different qualifications and has assisted in the development of learning outcomes approaches to qualifications. This is a necessary element for connecting validation to formal qualifications. Learning outcomes might be expressed in terms of what an individual knows, is able to do and understand irrespectively of the context and duration they have taken to learn it. However, most qualification frameworks in Europe still include only formal qualifications and there is no connection to other forms of certification or these parallel systems of credentials that operate at a sectoral level (Cedefop, 2019).

The qualification frameworks provide common reference standards in terms of learning outcomes that assists the individual to understand qualifications levels and how the different certifications relate to each other. These standards and learning outcomes serve as the basis for the assessment of learning outcomes that determines what an individual knows.

4.4 Assessment methodologies

Many of the assessment methodologies utilised to assess prior learning in a validation process are similar to those in formal education, such as paper and pencil tests (Cedefop et al., 2019). Thus, people that have had bad experiences in the past with formal assessment methods, might be in a disadvantage position also when going through validation as many might have developed negative attitudes and feelings towards similar forms of assessment. Increasing use of a variety of assessment methodologies might facilitate the success of less traditional students. However, less conventional methodologies might be perceived as less trustworthy or may not have been tested enough to prove their validity and reliability.

While traditional methods are in many instances used for validation, especially for summative approaches, they tend to be used in combination with other methods, such as interviews, portfolios or job examples. The portfolio method has been extensively documented as a tool for the development of validation. Skills assessment is growing considerably, and new forms of assessment are being developed with the assistance of computers and artificial intelligence. Corporate recruitment is using more and more sophisticated algorithms to determine the predictive value of skills and competences of the individual. Certificates and qualifications have become less relevant as employers are able on their own to evaluate the competences a candidate has in different ways. These methods are expensive to develop and more testing is needed to determine their validity and reliability, but there is little doubt that this might constitute an important venue for development.

5 A NEXT PHASE FOR VALIDATION?

The Recommendation of the Council of the European Union (2012), asked EU member states to put in place validation arrangements by 2018. From 2012 to 2018, European countries expanded and reformed their validation systems to different degrees (Cedefop et al., 2019). An evaluation of the Recommendation also shows that the definition and the four stages of validation put forward in 2012 have become a common reference for many countries; despite the different terminology it is possible to find certain common ground in the definition (Cedefop et al., 2019). The Recommendation (Council of the European Union, 2012), together with the EQF developments as well as the 2016 recommendation on upskilling (Council of the European Union, 2016) have provided an impetus for the development of validation, at least on a legislative, political level. These have consolidated the cooperation on a European level through the work of the European Qualifications Framework Advisory Group (EQF AG) and regular updates of the European inventory and the European Guidelines as well as forums like the Validation of Prior Learning Biennale, or the *Validation festival*.

Data from the European inventory shows that while most of the EU countries have in place some form for making skills acquired through non-formal and informal learning validated, the practices remain fragmented with different rationales and some lack of coherence (Cedefop et al., 2019). In addition, the use of validation and awareness of validation seems also to remain limited. However, the information in which these conclusions are founded is scarce. More needs to be done in the collection of information about participation in validation; evaluation research needs to be done more systematically. While some quantitative information is collected in a few countries, in most cases, the information available tends to be specific to parts of the validation system and holistic information is not available. This hinders our possibility to understand validation in its full potential.

Recent EU commitments to the skills agenda (European Commission, 2020b); the Osnabrück Declaration (Ministers in charge of vocational education and training of the Member States, EU Candidate Countries, EEA countries, the European social partners & European Commission, 2020); and other EU initiatives have validation embedded as a necessary element of lifelong learning policies interlinked to other activities and services. While the interconnection to other policies will be crucial to realise the full potential of validation, it will be important to maintain a clear focus on aspects that are intrinsic of the validation processes and that need specific attention and investment. The collaboration of research, practice and public policy is probably the only way forward.

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